

Living Lab on the FAO PMP-AMR assessment of the National Plan for Responsible AMU and Contrast AMR in the Italian Poultry Industry

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Poultry sector

Poultry

The Italian Living Lab (LL) on poultry production assessed the National Plan for the Responsible Use of Veterinary Medicines and Contrast Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) in the Poultry Industry. The assessment applied the methodology of the FAO Progressive Management Pathway for AMR (PMP-AMR) that, for the first time, was used to analyze a single livestock sector. The LL included twenty-four organizations representing all the relevant Italian stakeholders: i.e., five organizations from the poultry industry, two from the pharma industry, one retailer chain, one consumer association, three scientific and professional vet associations, four public vet labs (including the National Reference Centre for AMR and the ClassyFarm), the Ministries of Health and Agriculture, the Research Centre of the Ministry of Agriculture, the Regional Health Authorities of Emilia-Romagna and Veneto, the FAO, two academia and research institutions. Forty-eight experts and professionals were involved. The LL organized one main event (Rome, December 2021) and several restricted meetings to prepare discussions and finalize the results.

The strategy tested in the Living Lab

The National Plan is an initiative of the Italian association of the poultry industry (Unalitalia) supported by the Ministry of Health that started in 2015. In 2020, the plan achieved an AMU reduction of 88% in poultry farms (more than 90% in chickens) compared to the 2011 levels. The PMP-AMR is an assessment tool developed by FAO to support governments in implementing the National Action Plans (NAPs). The LL was the occasion to apply the PMP-AMR to a single livestock sector for the first time. The tool examines NAPs' measures under four aspects: AWARENESS (of stakeholders), EVIDENCE (monitoring AMU and AMR), PRACTICES (farms' animal health management), and GOVERNANCE (coordination of measures). The LL objectives were: to consolidate the national strategy to reduce AMU; (2) support the refinement of the FAO-PMP-AMR poultry-sector-specific component for further deployment in FAO Members; (3) assess the progress of implementation of the national AMR activities; and (4) agree on actions to be taken in the short term to enhance the plan.

The roadmap to implementation

The National Plan had a high PMP-AMR evaluation. Concerning the measures planned, compared to the FAO standards, the Plan reached an average fulfilment of 81% for AWARENESS, 82% for EVIDENCE, 94% for PRACTICES, and 67% for GOVERNANCE. Regarding the implementation of the measures, the scores were 75%, 68%, 89%, and 67% in the four intervention areas, respectively. The short-term actions envisaged to fill the gaps were: (1) for AWARENESS: assess the level of education on AMR at high school for zootechnicians and animal health operators; (2) for EVIDENCE: review/develop AMR surveillance on the poultry farms' environment; Develop national reporting of AMR surveillance in bacterial pathogens associated with clinical cases; and conduct AM residue testing in the environment; (3) for PRACTICES: set up a benchmarking system for veterinarians through ClassyFarm; implement regulation to guide high users identified through the benchmarking system; (4) for GOVERNANCE: allocate national funding for AMR/AMU research in the poultry sector. During the LL, the participant experts identified the organizations responsible for the envisaged actions (mostly public health entities).

The impact created by the Living Lab

- AMU: The LL brought all the main Italian stakeholders to discuss with FAO experts the adequacy of the Poultry National Plan to the global objectives of the Quadripartite and FAO Action Plans. The PMP-AMR assessment showed that the National Plan promoted by Unalitalia meets the best international standards for these actions. A confirmation of the relevant results already obtained by Italian poultry farms in reducing the total AMU and the usage of Critically Important Antimicrobials (CIAs). The weaknesses highlighted in the LL mostly call the public animal health operators to activate the necessary measures to fill the existing gaps. The Poultry National Plan anticipated by a few years the issue of the first Italian National Plan against AMR (PNCAR 2017). The LL allowed national health authorities to receive the poultry sector's expectations regarding the new PNCAR (2023-2025), whose draft is currently under examination by regional administrations.
- Animal Health, costs and savings: the suggested improvements imply positive effects on farm health management and the costs of animal diseases.

Challenges

The capacity of animal public health authorities and the other public bodies involved to implement the envisaged improvements, especially regarding: (1) the systematic monitoring and reporting of AMR related to the poultry farm environment and supply chain and from clinical cases; (2) the benchmarking of vet prescription activities and the consequent corrective actions; (3) the allocation of national funding for AMR research specific for the poultry sector.

Successes

(1) Succeed in bringing together all the most relevant stakeholders of the poultry industry, despite their divergent business and professional interests; (2) Engage all stakeholders to address the highest international standards for national action plans against AMR and jointly identify actions that can further improve the good results already achieved; (3) Provide indications to the public health authorities for the renewal of the PNCAR in the 2023-2025 period.

The LL has been an effective tool to independently assess the relevant improvements of the Italian poultry sector in AMR and AMU in the last decade and to identify margins for further progress.

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